

OceanOS

AI-driven insights to
secure the future of our
marine environments

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CASE STUDY

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Industries such as offshore energy are facing increasing regulatory requirements to minimise their environmental impact. With marine habitats under severe threat from climate change and human activity, there is a pressing need to balance the transition to renewables with the protection of our ocean ecosystems.

OceanOS, a marine biodiversity startup founded in 2022, gives governments, businesses and conservation organisations unparalleled insights into ocean health. The company's data-driven, AI-powered tools are changing the way we monitor, analyse and protect our precious underwater environments.

“Our mission is to enable nature-positive operations in the oceans. How we achieve that is through our state-of-the-art biodiversity monitoring system, which combines acoustic, imagery, eDNA and environmental data to provide a holistic, in-situ picture of what’s going on underwater.”

Vincent Opitz

Co-founder of OceanOS

OceanOS' current primary market is offshore wind. Offshore wind is viewed as a key pillar in the transition to renewable energy globally, with the UK government previously setting a production target of 50 gigawatts by 2030. But as the appetite for offshore wind farms increases, so does the pressure to evidence and minimise their environmental impact.

Vincent, who leads on strategy and product development at OceanOS, says: “Traditional methods of gathering the required biodiversity data for regulatory purposes, such as bottom trawling or manual wildlife spotting, are cumbersome, expensive and often invasive or unsafe. By deploying our tools via remote sensors, developers can gather much richer data, much more efficiently. We are enabling them to meet regulatory requirements and also become better stewards of our marine resources.”

Turning AI from ambition to reality

Vincent and co-founder David Lamb – an experienced mechanical engineer – always knew they wanted OceanOS to be an AI-first company, seeing the huge potential of these technologies to strengthen their data-gathering and analysis products. But as a small team with minimal background in AI, they needed support.

“That’s why we’ve been looking to programmes such as BridgeAI for guidance and advice on how to integrate AI and machine learning into our platform. On one hand, we knew AI could massively reduce the time required to process the vast and varied marine data we collect from remote sensors. On the other, it could help us to spot patterns in the data or make predictions about future ecological states, and therefore enhance the insights we are able to offer our customers.”

Vincent Opitz
Co-founder of OceanOS

Applying existing machine learning algorithms to video data from underwater cameras, for example, could realise benefits such as improving image quality in a messy environment or identifying individual species of fish in a particular area. Building bespoke AI models, meanwhile, offers the chance not only to better understand the similarities and differences between varied datasets, but to make predictions from baseline and comparative data about the impact a proposed development might have on aspects of the marine environment.

From recruitment to use cases

The impact of the Independent Scientific Advisor programme

To help achieve its advanced data science and AI adoption ambitions, the OceanOS team enlisted the guidance of The Alan Turing Institute's Independent Scientific Advisor (ISA) programme, in partnership with BridgeAI. Via this programme, OceanOS was paired with Dr Rachael Stickland, a Data Wrangler and Scientist at the Turing Institute. An expert on the delivery of high-quality, analysis-ready data – a crucial step in OceanOS' goal of providing its customers with valuable data-derived insights – Rachael supported the team in a range of ways in her 16 weeks as the company's primary ISA. That support included:

- reflecting on skills gaps within the company, and reviewing and sharing job adverts
- taking part in an interview panel for a data scientist role and reviewing a technical task
- linking OceanOS with wider networks and groups in the AI and data sector
- sharing training resources, funding opportunities and events related to the company's goals
- advising on the quality and quantity of data required for OceanOS' desired biodiversity models.

"I connected with OceanOS at a time of high activity – new projects were starting, funding applications were being written, and staff were being recruited. Balancing the need for growth with the uncertainty around deploying AI models can be a challenge for smaller startups, and knowledge of AI – including its feasible and responsible applications – varies widely across SMEs. But the team at OceanOS had a willingness to engage, an openness to learn and the ability to act upon advice, making our conversations enjoyable and fruitful."

Dr Rachael Stickland

Data Wrangler and Scientist, The Alan Turing Institute

Additionally, Rachael introduced the OceanOS team to another Turing-BridgeAI ISA, Dr Andy Corbett, Head of Research and Development at deeptech company digiLab. Making use of his expertise in machine learning and neural networks, Andy shared examples of computer vision techniques being used in other marine biodiversity projects and helped the OceanOS team to work through their goals and options in AI modelling.

“Working with Rachael and Andy has been really beneficial. They helped with things like the recruitment of our new Head of Science, Laurens Geffert, who is a perfect match for us, and challenging us to think deeply about how we want to apply AI models in our work. As we continue to invest in ecological modelling and deepen our understanding of ecosystem dynamics, I believe there is significant potential to unlock even greater positive outcomes from these relationships, fostering collaboration and innovation in meaningful ways.”

Vincent Opitz

Co-founder of OceanOS

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This work is led by **Dr. Vera Matser**, Head of Skills and Principal Investigator for BridgeAI at The Alan Turing Institute.

For any comments, questions, or collaboration opportunities with BridgeAI, please email: bridgeai@turing.ac.uk.

Authors and Contributors

Stuart Gillespie: Technical Writer (0009-0003-1402-0184)

Vincent Opitz: OceanOS, Cofounder

Laurens Geffert: OceanOS, Head of Science

Rachael Stickland: The Alan Turing Institute, Independent Scientific Advisor for BridgeAI (0000-0003-3398-4272)

Andrew Corbett: The Alan Turing Institute, Independent Scientific Advisor for BridgeAI (0000-0002-3425-7205)

Alexandra Araujo Alvarez: The Alan Turing Institute, Senior Research Project Manager (0009-0008-6607-3815)

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